

Exploring The Impact Of Social Isolation And Trauma On Mental Health Challenges Among Undergraduate Students In Tertiary Institution In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study explores the impact of social isolation and trauma on mental health challenges among undergraduate students in Rivers State. Correlational research design was used for the study. The aim of the study was to determine the relationship between psychosocial predictors and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. A sample of 1, 324 undergraduate students was used to compose the sample. The multistage sampling technique was used. Two research questions were answered while two corresponding null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Instruments for data collection as titled Psychosocial Predictors Questionnaire and Mental Health Challenges Scale comprising of a 21 Item self-report inventory known as DASS-Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scales were used. The instruments were validated by three experts in measurement and evaluation. The coefficient of reliability for the two instruments were done using the Cronbach Alpha Reliability method of internal consistency, psychosocial predictors questionnaire 0.835 and mental health challenges scale 0.911 were obtained. The research questions were answered using simple regression while the null hypotheses were tested using t-test associated with simple regression. Findings revealed among others that there is a low and negatively significant prediction between social isolation and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State, while trauma showed a low and weak positive relationship which does not significantly predicts mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that students should build strong positive social support network to ward off the negative effects of social isolation, parents should build a strong supportive network or relationship between them and their children and professional counsellors and mental health experts or specialists and health care providers should tailor interventions towards organizing seminars, workshops, counselling sessions/ psycho education and screening tests for students with substance use or alcohol use disorder. And also, those with these mental health challenges can also be provided with medical care and intervention in a mental health facility with the support of their parents.

Keywords: Social Isolation, Trauma, Mental Health Challenges, Undergraduate Students

INTRODUCTION

Tertiary education is not just advantageous to an individual but also the society at large. Graduates of tertiary institutions are more environmentally conscious, have healthier habits and have a higher level of

civic participation. This can only be possible if such undergraduate students are healthy in mind, body and spirit. The role of these institutions in the overall development of students is vital, as university life is a period of personal growth, academic pressure, and the formation of professional identities. However, transitioning to university life often involves various psychosocial trauma that can significantly affect students' mental health. Stressors such as social challenges, and personal expectations are common sources of stress for undergraduate students (Roth & Brooks-Kempler, 2023). If not properly managed, these psychosocial challenges can hinder students' mental well-being. If these students are faced with one of these mental health challenge or the other, they may become socially isolated which will in turn be difficult for them to become active, productive and functional members of their society.

Mental health can be seen as a continuous experience, where an individual's mental health may have many different possible values (Keyes, 2002). Mental wellness is viewed as a positive characteristic, this definition of mental health explains emotional well-being, the capacity to live a full and creative life, and the flexibility to deal with life's inevitable challenges. Some discussions are formulated in terms of contentment or happiness (Graham, 2014). Many therapeutic difficulties and self-help books offer techniques and philosophies espousing strategies and techniques vaunted as effective for further encouraging mental wellness. Positive psychology is increasingly important in mental health.

Mental health challenge is a concept that existed over a long period of time. It is used to describe a problem or distress an individual is going through emotionally, socially, psychologically, among others that makes it difficult for an individual to carry out his or her daily activities effectively. It could also be detrimental to the overall wellbeing of the individual involved. According to World Health Organization (2021), a mental health challenge is known by a clinically significant disturbance in an individual's cognition, emotional regulation, or behaviour. It is usually connected with distress or impairment in critical areas of functioning. There are various types of mental health challenges. Mental health challenges could also be known as mental health conditions. The latter is a wider term used to describe psychosocial disabilities and other mental states linked with significant distress, impairment in functioning, or danger of self-harm. This study focuses on mental disorders as described by the International Classification of Diseases 11th Revision (ICD – 11). These mental health challenges are; social isolation, depression, bipolar disorder, post-traumatic stress disorder, among others.

Social isolation is a state of complete or near-complete lack of contact between an individual and society. It varies from loneliness, which shows temporary and involuntary lack of contact with other humans in the world (York, & Waite, 2009). Social isolation can be a problem for individuals of any age, though symptoms may vary by age group (Khullar, 2016).

Social isolation has similar characteristics in both temporary instances and for those with a historical lifelong isolation cycle. All types of social isolation can include staying home for lengthy periods of time, having no communication with family, acquaintances or friends, and/or willfully avoiding any contact with other humans when those chances come up. This can happen as a result of involuntary circumstances like school bullying, peer exclusion, hospitalization, institutionalization or absence / incarceration of family members or due to voluntary social withdrawal from interacting or relating with others to avoid bullying, frustrations, social anxiety or stress. (Mathews, 2017, Morese, Defedele and Nervo, 2018).

In the discipline of developmental psychology, involuntary social withdrawal is seen as equal to social isolation or social disaffection suffered by children and adolescents particularly in schools, who are characterized by certain shyness, asocialness, unsociability, aloneness and peer avoidance (Coplan & Rubin, 2010). Social isolation coming from peer exclusion may not necessarily lead to a sense of loneliness particularly when youths feel that some close associates of theirs and adult mentors are still around to listen and help. However, when the quantity of interpersonal network or link is reduced and the quality of social support is not sufficient, socially withdrawn children and youths are more likely to be at risk of developing appropriate social and interpersonal mechanisms necessary for engaging in positive interaction with peers in school or community gatherings.

Youths who are going through social isolation in the form of social withdrawal are seen to exhibit socially avoidant behavior and their invisibility from the care of helping professionals or care givers and the

scrutiny of the public (Wong, 2012, Wong, 2014). Young people who separate themselves from others at home are said to be asocial in behaviour and relationship and thereby been quietly trapped in the state of socialness without enjoying much emotional and instrumental support. However, in the case of youths who are going through a psychological problem, physical illness or disability, which has prevented or stopped them from taking part in the community, they would not be considered as “pure” or “primary” social withdrawal cases. They are instead considered as secondary social withdrawal cases as a result of primary psychological or physical challenges (Suwa et al, 2003).

Alsadoun et al (2023) did a study on social isolation among adolescents and its association with depression symptoms. The result of this study revealed that prevalence of social isolation among adolescents was 10.14%. The prevalence of depression symptoms among adolescents was high (31.68%), There was a significant association between social isolation and symptoms of depression among the studied sample ($\chi^2 12.3, p=0.002$). It was found that being a male, living with both parents, and having low income are significant predictors of social isolation among adolescents; with 20,08 and p value < 0001 . It was also found that low-income level had a more impact on social isolation among adolescents than other factors (estimate 16).

Also, Almeida et al (2022) did a study on social isolation and its impacts on child and adolescent development in China: a systemic review of 519 studies were screened and 12 were included in the systematic review. Five of those focused on psychology and social issues, two of them on the effects of pandemics on these issues reported on impacts on general health and two consequences over the hypothalamus- hypophysis-adrenal axis and the cognitive and social development. The review shows a strong association between social isolation and anxiety and depression in children and adolescent. Social isolation leads to higher level of cortisol and worse cognitive development. Therefore, the mental and physical health of children and adolescents need a careful follow up by health professionals during and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Prizeman, Weinstein and MacCabe (2023) did a study on effects of mental health stigma on loneliness, social isolation, and relationships in young people with depression symptoms. In-depth semi-structured interviews with $N= 22$ years) who reported high symptoms of depression (mood and feelings questionnaire (MFQ) score > 27) (i.e community sample, $N = 9$) or had been previously diagnosed with depression by a medical professional (i.e clinical sample, $N= 13$). In other words, social withdrawal is not mainly a mental health or disability challenge or condition, but an atomic behavioural response to difficulties faced by youths (Furlong, 2008). However, it is very possible for primary social withdrawal cases to develop symptoms of depression or social anxiety if they are left alone. Thus, this situation can lead to mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Psychological trauma (mental trauma, psychotrauma, or psychiatric trauma) is an emotional response caused by severe distressing events that are outside the normal range of human experiences, such as experiencing violence, rape, or a terrorist attack. The event must be understood by the affected person as directly threatening the affected person or their loved ones with death, severe bodily injury, or sexual violence, indirect exposure, such as from watching television news, may be extremely distressing and can produce an involuntary and possibly overwhelming physiological stress response, but does not produce trauma per se. (DSM-5,2021)

Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) and other mental health challenges are very common in high conflict – affected areas. (Charlson et al, 2019). PTSD may come up as a result of exposure to an extremely terrifying situation or series of occurrences that are negative. It is known by all of the following: 1) reexperiencing the traumatic situation or occurrence in the present (intrusive memories, flashbacks, or nightmares); 2) avoidance of thoughts and memories of the event(s), or avoidance of activities, circumstances, or persons reminding one of the occurrences; and 3) persistent or continuous views of in-present threat. These signs continue for at least many weeks and causes significant impairment in functioning. There are certain factors that could cause mental health challenges for undergraduate students in tertiary institutions these factors could be psychological and also social in nature. They include social isolation, parent – child interaction, trauma, academic stress among others.

Trauma is a type of distressing or troubling event or experience that can have an impact on a person's ability to cope and function. Trauma can result in emotional, physical and psychological harm. Various persons will face some kind of traumatic event from the unexpected death of a loved one to a motor vehicle accident at some point in their lifetime. However, not all people will encounter Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) after a traumatic event (National Institute of Mental Health, 2023).

Although someone might not develop or have PTSD, they may still encounter PTSD-like symptoms immediately after a traumatic event. Many of these symptoms are actually common reactions to a traumatic event (Centre for Disease Control and Prevention, 2023). Substance use can lead to drug induced hallucinations and psychosis like cannabis, which can also cause anxiety which are mental health challenges that can affect an undergraduate student in a tertiary institution where the student lacks the ability to concentrate on his or her study leading to poor grades and eventually such a student may drop out of school because he or she can no longer cope. Depression, anxiety, and even suicidal ideation may set in which are mental health challenges for undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Trauma comes in various shapes and forms, but there are some common scenarios that are predominantly considered as traumatic. Types of traumatic events or incidents that a person may experience at some point in life include:

Abuse, Assault, Car accident, Death of a loved one, Divorce, Family or parental abandonment, Imprisonment, Job loss, Natural disaster, Physical injury, Rape, Serious illness, Terrorism, Violence and Witnessing a crime, accident or death.

Trauma often falls into one of three various categories or groups, some traumas such as accident or natural disasters are one-time events or occurrences that are reduced in duration and scope. Other traumas are long-lasting and on-going such as coping with a chronic illness or dealing with repeated domestic abuse. There are also types of trauma that are many times ignored, such as trauma that occurs during child birth or surgery. There are, however, some common symptoms that may be expected to occur after a traumatic event. The following are common reactions to trauma: After a traumatic event or occurrence, it is common experience to witness some intrusive thoughts and memories of the traumatic event. This is especially likely to occur when one face something (for instance a person, place or image) that reminds one of the traumatic event. It is also very natural to feel more on guard and aware of one's surroundings after a traumatic occurrence. This is actually a very protective symptom as one's body is attempting or trying to keep one safe by making one more aware of potential sources of threat and danger. This natural safety mechanism is going to be more sensitive following a traumatic event. Just as one is going to likely be more on-guard, one is also likely going to feel more keyed-up and on edge following a traumatic event. This is again part of one's body natural protection system, fear, and anxiety tell one that there is some kind of danger present and all the bodily sensations that go along with fear and anxiety are essentially designed or fashioned to help one respond to that danger. They are preparing one to flee, freeze, or to fight following a traumatic event, one's body alarm system is going to be more sensitive in an attempt to protect or defend one from future traumatic events.

After a traumatic event, one's assumptions about the world being a safe and secure place are understandably destroyed. Consequently, people may feel as though any situation or place is potentially unsafe. Places or situations one felt secured in, may now feel threatening and be anxiety provoking. This is especially likely to happen in situations or places that remind one of a traumatic event. The symptoms presented below can be a sign that one may be at risk for developing PTSD (Miao et al, 2018). They may cause the expected trauma symptoms listed above to become worse, eventually leading to PTSD. Therefore, it is very important to be aware of the following symptoms. It is important to keep an eye or watch out for a loss of interest in activities that one used to once enjoy, as well as feelings of being detached from others. This symptom can be a sign that one is at risk of becoming depressed. This symptom may also cause one to isolate oneself from others, including important sources of social support. Xia et al (2023) conducted a study on relationship between childhood trauma and mental health during the Covid-19 pandemic: a network analysis. A total of 1,247 college students were recruited and were asked to complete a series of questionnaires, including the childhood trauma questionnaire, patient health

questionnaire. Generalized Anxiety Disorder Scale, Post-traumatic stress checklist- Civilian version, and fear of Covid-19 scale. The Gaussian graphical model with the scores of the questionnaires as nodes was estimated. The partial correlations between nodes were calculated as edges. Moreover, network comparison tests were conducted to compare the network patterns between participants with high levels of childhood trauma exhibiting the strongest strength and the highest expected impact in the network. Participants with high levels of childhood trauma and participants with low levels of childhood trauma showed comparable network structure and global strength. The findings of this study revealed a complicated network pattern between childhood trauma and different or various mental health problems, depicting that childhood trauma might be a risk factor for mental health during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Also, Garrido, et al (2023) did a study on association between childhood trauma and mental disorder in adolescents during the second pandemic wave of Covid-19, Chiclayo-Peru. The study employed a cross-sectional secondary data study measuring childhood trauma using the Marshall 5 trauma scale, depressive symptomatology (GAD-7). The results revealed that depressive symptomatology prevalence was 76.3%, 95% ci: 72.14-80.15) and increased by 23% in school children with childhood trauma (PR: 1.23; 95% ci: 1-10-1.37). Factors positively associated with depressive symptomatology included increasing age, seeking mental health help during the pandemic, and severe family dysfunctions. Anxiety symptomatology prevalence was 62.3% (95% CI: 57.65-66.75) and increased by 55% in school children with childhood trauma (PR: 1.55; 95% CI: 1.31-1.85). Anxiety symptomatology was positively associated with mild moderate, and severe family dysfunction school children exposed to childhood trauma are at increased risk for depressive and anxiety symptoms.

After a traumatic event, it is common to avoid certain circumstances or situations, activities or engagements or people. However, one must pay attention to avoidance behaviours. Avoidance usually lead to more avoidance as it reinforces the belief that the world is not a safe place. This avoidance can then lead to a worsening of symptoms and eventually PTSD. Just as avoidance of activities, situations or people can be problematic, so can be avoidance of thought and feelings, the symptoms people face after a traumatic event can be very distressing or difficult. As a result, people may depend on unhealthy coping mechanism (for instance, using substances) as a way of avoiding these symptoms. Avoidance is only a short-term solution and in the long run, it can actually cause one's feelings and thoughts to become more intense or severe. This situation can lead to mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Therefore, this study intends to explore the impact of social isolation and trauma on mental health challenges among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

In recent times, the researcher observed that some undergraduate students at a point can no longer cope with their school or academic programmes and they begin to drop out of school. They also begin to experience discrimination and stigmatization from family members or relatives and also their friends leading to the lack of social support at some point. Some undergraduate students who are not able to cope with all of these challenges may begin to have suicidal tendencies or ideation, some even get to commit suicide. They also suffer from brain disorders or problems. These undergraduate students go as far as stealing money from anywhere just to ensure they remain on drugs to avoid withdrawal symptoms. They lack concentration in whatever they are doing. They cannot do any meaningful work. Some of these youth become anti-social beings because they break the law of any institution they find themselves and begin to exhibit criminal tendencies and even go as far as committing all manner of crimes without any remorse. What then could be responsible for all these? Could it be a result of some psychosocial factors like social isolation, and trauma among others? It is against this backdrop that this paper explores the impact of social isolation and trauma on mental health challenges among undergraduate students in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study explores the impact of social isolation and trauma on mental health challenges among undergraduate students in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of this study are;

1. To investigate the extent to which social isolation predicts mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

2. To assess the extent to which trauma predicts mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study;

1. To what extent does social isolation predicts mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
2. To what limit does trauma predicts mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance;

1. Social isolation does not significantly predict mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant prediction between trauma and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The Correlational research design was adopted in the study. This design is considered appropriate since the researcher is interested in exploring the impact of social isolation and trauma on mental health challenges among undergraduate students in Rivers State. The population of the study comprised all 78, 525 undergraduate students in the three government owned universities in Rivers State and two polytechnics in Rivers State. The sample size for the study was 1, 324 Undergraduate Students in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. Stratified random sampling technique was employed to randomly select the institution based on their respective institutions (universities and polytechnics) and the simple random sampling technique was also used to draw two departments from each of the faculties from the five tertiary institutions. These departments have specific number of students which the researcher made use of (Uniport – 353, RSU- 478, IAUE- 122, KenSarowiwa Poly – 200 and Captain Elechi Amadi Poly- 171) giving a sum total of 1, 324 for the sample. The instruments for data collection were the Psychosocial Predictors' Questionnaire (PPQ) and the mental health challenges scale (comprising of Depression, anxiety, stress scales) a 21- item self-reporting scale (DASS- 21). The Psychosocial Predictors' Questionnaire had 2 sections and each section had 5 parts each. Each part measured each of the 2 psychosocial predictors' variables. The first section measured social isolation, and the second measured trauma which has physical trauma containing 5 parts, emotional trauma containing 5 parts also and sexual trauma also having 4 parts. The researcher made use of adapted scales like the trauma scale. This scale is a 4 point Likert scale type which is designated as Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3 Disagree (D) = 2 and strongly Disagree (SD) = 1.

The mental health challenges scale is a standized instrument which is represented as Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS) by Lovibond & Lovibond (1995) a self – report questionnaire consisting of 21 items that assess various symptoms of depression, anxiety and stress. Each of the three DASS- 21 scales contain 7 items, divided into subscales with similar content. The DASS 21 is based on a dimensional rather than a categories conception of psychological disorder. The instrument is an adapted instrument because the researcher made slight changes to the instrument to suit her work that is she rearranged the subscales in an orderly manner. The rating scale is as follows: 0= did not apply to me at all, 1= applied to me to some degree, or some of the time, 2= applied to me to a considerable degree or a good part of time and 3= applied to me very much or most of the time. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity while Cronbach alpha was used to check the internal consistency of the instrument to guarantee the use of the instrument for the study. The reliability coefficients obtained for the two instruments were; psychosocial predictors' questionnaire 0.835 and mental health challenges scale 0.911. The instrument was administered to the students by the researcher, assisted by two trained research assistants. Copies of the instruments were retrieved after students had given their responses. Data collected was analyzed using Simple regression Statistic in Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The r- Value (coefficient) of

Simple regression Statistic was used to answer the research questions based on the interpretation scale while the null hypotheses was tested using t- test associated with simple regression at .05 alpha level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question One: *To what extent does social isolation predict mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Simple Regression Analysis on the extent social isolation predicted mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	-.060 ^a	.004	.003	.47440

Table 1 revealed that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be 0.060 while the regression squared value was computed to be 0.004. This shows that there is a low and negative prediction between social isolation and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Judging by the coefficient of determination which is 0.4% change in mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State can be predicted by social isolation, while 99.6% was accounted for by other variables not considered in this study.

Research Question Two: *To what extent does trauma predict mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Simple Regression Analysis on the extent trauma predicted mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.053 ^a	.003	.002	.47457

Table 2 revealed that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be 0.053 while the regression squared value was computed to be 0.003. This shows that there is a low and weak positive prediction between trauma and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Judging by the coefficient of determination which is 0.3% change in mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State can be predicted by trauma, while 99.7% was accounted for other variables not considered in this study.

Hypothesis One: Social isolation does not significantly predict mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

Table 3: T-test associated with Simple Regressions on how social isolation predicts mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.084	.077		27.007	.000
	Social Isolation	-.056	.026	-.060	-2.167	.030

Table 3 shows that the t-test calculated for social isolation is -2.167 and the significant P-value of 0.030, is lower than 0.05 level of significance (P<0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, this implies that social isolation significantly predicts mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Two: Trauma does not significantly predict mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

Table 4: T-test associated with Simple Regressions on how trauma predicts mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.005	.046		43.328	.000
	Trauma	-.065	.034	-.053	-1.938	.053

Table 4 shows that the t-test calculated for trauma is -1.938 and the significant P-value of 0.053, is greater than 0.05 level of significance ($P > 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, this implies that trauma does not significantly predict mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Social isolation and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

There is a low negative prediction between social isolation and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State and the prediction is statistically significant. This finding is in alignment with the views of Alsadoun et al (2023) who posited or asserted that there was a significant association between social isolation and symptoms of depression among the studied sample. The finding also aligned with the view of Almeida et al (2020) which showed a strong association between social isolation, anxiety and depression in children and adolescents. Prizeman, Weinstein and MacCabe (2023) carried out a study on effects of mental health stigma on loneliness, social isolation and relationships in young people with depression symptoms they reported high symptoms of depression (mood and feelings) which is in alignment with the above findings. The difference in result of the study is probably because undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State may want to isolate themselves from public associations to attend to more meaningful things.

Trauma and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

There is a low and positive prediction between trauma and mental health challenges among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. But the prediction is not statistically significant. The finding is in alignment with Xia et al (2023) who conducted a study on prediction between childhood trauma and mental health during the Covid -19 pandemic: a network analysis. The findings of this study revealed a complicated network pattern between childhood trauma and different mental health problems, depicting that childhood trauma might be a risk factor for mental health during the Covid – 19 pandemic. This finding also agrees with the views of Garrido et al (2023) who carried out a study on association between childhood trauma and mental disorder in adolescents during the second pandemic wave of Covid- 19, Chilayo- Peru. Anxiety symptomology was positively associated with mild, moderate and severe family dysfunction, school children exposed to childhood trauma are at increased risk for depressive and anxiety symptoms. The result from the existing research differs from the above findings probably because undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State may not have had traumatic experiences leading to mental health challenges.

CONCLUSION

This study explores the impact of social isolation and trauma on mental health challenges among undergraduate students in Rivers State. The findings revealed that students face various psychosocial problems, including trauma from economic difficulties, interpersonal conflicts, and societal expectations. When these challenges are not effectively managed, they significantly undermine mental health, leading to increased anxiety, depression, and burnout, which negatively impact academic performance and overall life satisfaction. Adaptive strategies, such as problem-solving, seeking social support, managing time

effectively, and engaging in recreational activities, were found to promote resilience and emotional stability. In contrast, maladaptive strategies, such as avoidance, and withdrawal, intensified stress worsened mental well-being. The study also emphasized the importance of institutional support systems, including counseling services, mentorship programs, and mental health awareness initiatives, in enhancing students' ability to manage psychosocial challenges. The findings highlight the urgent need for tertiary institutions to integrate comprehensive mental health interventions and adaptive coping strategies into their institution.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings the following recommendations were made:

1. Students should build strong positive social support network to ward off the negative effects of social isolation.
2. Parents should build a strong supportive network or relationship between them and their children.
3. Professional counsellors and mental health experts or specialist and health care providers should tailor interventions towards organizing seminars, workshops, counselling sessions/ psycho education and screening tests for students with substance use or alcohol use disorder. And also those with these mental health challenges can also be provided with medical care and intervention in a mental health facility with the support of their parents.
4. Students who are faced with traumatic issues or problems should go to their counselling units for therapy and other interventions.

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